

Quantitative micro level determination of B group vitamins by differential pulse polarography

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Abstract : A comprehensive voltammetric study of B group water soluble vitamins using differential pulse polarography (DPP) has enabled their determination at very low concentration in pharmaceutical preparations. The data demonstrated that the results of vitamin estimation were quantitative and in good agreement in terms of measurement.

Keywords : Pulse polarography, vitamins, micro-determination.

The constant evaluation of real composition in pharmaceutical preparations at sub-micro levels has gained wide attention for sensitive and accurate analytical methods because of their great relevance to health and substantial physiological effects¹. In addition the choice of appropriate procedure to solve an analytical problem in these cases is often controlled by the sample matrix, and also the amount of preparation that is needed before the measurement². For this purpose, mainly four instrumental techniques namely spectrophotometric^{3,4}, chromatographic^{5,6}, radiometric^{7,8} and electrochemical^{9,10} are used. The electroanalytical methods with wide dynamic linear range of determination between 10^{-3} – 10^{-10} M have proved to be superior to classical wet analysis due to great care of sample preparation and lack of interference from incipients in dosage form¹¹. In the present work attention was focused on trace determination of water soluble B group vitamins mainly thiamine 3-[(4-amino-methyl-5-pyrimidinyl)methyl]-5-(2-hydroxyethyl)-4-methylthioazolium chloride, riboflavin (7,8-dimethyl-10-dibutyl isoalloxazine and pyridoxine-(5-hydroxy-6-methyl-3,4-pyridine dimethanol). A lot of pharmaceutical preparations contain B₁, B₂ and B₆ either solely (single vitamin) or multivitamins i.e. B complex. In such case, analytical method for their estimation has to be selective owing to the possible interference¹². We have made an attempt to develop optimum voltammetric conditions for the determination of vitamin B₁, B₂ and B₆ individually as well as in presence of each other using differential pulse polarography (DPP).

Results and discussion

Polarographic characteristics and optimization of voltammetric conditions : Preliminary electrochemical investigations of thiamine, riboflavin and pyridoxine on a

dropping mercury electrode have shown the suitability of 0.1 M potassium chloride among other various supporting electrolytes examined such as hydrochloric acid, lithium chloride, lithium sulfate, acetate buffer and ammonium carbonate. DC polarographic (DCP) and DPP observations are described in Table 1. All measurements were therefore made in 0.1 M KCl. Thiamine, riboflavin and pyridoxine gave well-defined polarographic waves and DP peaks in this medium. Peak currents were increased linearly with the concentration of these vitamins and thus were found suitable for quantitative determinations. The calibration characteristics are included in Table 2. The detection limit of 0.9, 0.2 and 0.8 µg/ml were achieved for vitamin B₁, B₂ and B₆, respectively.

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics of B group vitamins in 0.1 M KCl

Sl. no.	Vitamin	DCP		DPP	
		$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	i_d (µA)	$-E_p$ (V)	I_p (µA)
1.	Thiamine	1.16	0.12	1.16	14.8
2.	Riboflavin	0.18	0.10	0.11	9.2
3.	Pyridoxine	1.41	0.31	1.46	8.5

Thiamine = 0.5×10^{-5} M, riboflavin = 1×10^{-3} M, pyridoxine = 1×10^{-3} M, DCP, direct current polarography. $E_{1/2}$, half-wave potential.

Analytical applications : DP peaks of thiamine, riboflavin and pyridoxine in 0.1 M KCl were found distinguishable due to their well-separated peak potentials. It was made the basis for determination of vitamins B₁, B₂ and B₆ individually and in presence of each other. Synthetic mixtures were prepared in laboratory by adding known concen-

tration of vitamins. These were analysed using DPP under these experimental conditions. Concentrations determined are given in Table 3.

Table 2. Calibration characteristics of vitamin B₁, B₂ and B₆ in 0.1 M KCl

Sl. no.	Vitamin	Linearity range (ppm)	Slope × 10 ⁻³	Coefficient correlation (r)	Standard deviation (±)
1.	Thiamine	0.9–120	0.3129	0.9985	0.09
2.	Riboflavin	0.2–40	0.3996	0.9938	0.04
3.	Pyridoxine	0.8–50	0.5762	0.9516	0.30

Table 3. Analysis of test solution of B group vitamins by DPP

Sl. no.	Vitamin	Conc. (µg/ml)		Recovery (%)
		Present	Determined ^a	
1.	Thiamine	0.9	0.89	98.88
2.	Riboflavin	1.0	0.98	98.00
3.	Pyridoxine	0.8	0.79	98.75

^aAverage of three determinations.

Determination of vitamin B₁, B₂ and B₆ in pharmaceutical preparations : The prepared samples of multivitamin preparation (Polybion and Becosule) were taken into the polarographic medium and DP polarograms were recorded from +0.05 V to -1.6 V. Peak currents were measured at -1.16, -0.11 and -1.46 V for vitamin B₁, B₂ and B₆, respectively after making blank corrections. Concentrations were determined by standard addition method¹³. Generally two additions were made for quantitation. Results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. DPP determination of vitamin B₁, B₂ and B₆

Sl. no. sample	Pharmaceutical					
	B ₁		B ₂		B ₆	
	Vit. conc. (µg/ml) ^a	Er. (%)	Vit. conc. (µg/ml) ^a	Er. (%)	Vit. conc. (µg/ml) ^a	Er. (%)
1. Polybion	9.96 (10)	0.4	9.98 (10)	0.2	2.98 (3)	0.7
2. Becosule	9.88 (10)	1.2	9.91 (10)	0.9	2.91 (3)	3.0

Er : Percent relative error.

^aAverage of three determinations, values shown in parentheses is concentration of vitamin cited on multivitamin preparation.

The results obtained by DPP method suggests the validity of determination in accordance with the cited values on pharmaceutical preparations.

Conclusion :

DPP provides a simple approach for the determination of B group vitamins at sub micro levels. Peak potential separation has further been enabled simultaneous determination of vitamin B₁, B₂ and B₆ without any interference. The results obtained of multivitamin analysis has also revealed that the recoveries (98.0–98.88%) were quantitative. The

suggested method will be useful in pharmaceutical and biomedical laboratories for rapid assessment of composition of the prescribed dosages.

Experimental

Instrumentation : A polarographic analyzer (Model 174-A) in conjunction with a drop timer (Model 174/70) and X-Y recorder (Model RE 0074), all of Princeton Applied Research Corporation, EG & G, U.S.A., was used for DC and DPP experiments. The instrumental settings for DPP were as follows : a dropping mercury electrode (DME) was used as the working electrode, modulation amplitude, 50 mV; pulse duration, 57 ms; clock time, 1 s and scan rate, 5 mV/s. Potentials were measured against an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. A platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode in all observations.

All the experiments were carried out at 25 ± 1 °C. The solutions were deaerated by bubbling purified nitrogen for 20 min prior to voltammetric recordings. Nitrogen was purified by passing it through a vanadous chloride solution. All chemicals used were of reagent grade purity. Solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water.

Sample preparation : The trade named multivitamin B complex preparations Polybion and Becosule were dissolved thoroughly in doubly distilled water. These were filtered and made up to the requisite volume¹⁴. The details of vitamin samples were as follows :

Polybion : (batch no. F-1041804) was of Merck (Mumbai) with a composition of thiamine (10 mg), riboflavin (10 mg), pyridoxine HU (3 mg), ascorbic acid (150 mg), nicotinamide (100 mg), cyanocobalamine (15 mcg), calcium pantothenate (50 mg), folic acid (15 mg), biotin (100 mg). **Becosule :** (batch no. 520-29033B) was of Omni Protech (Mumbai) with a composition of thiamine mono nitrate (10 mg), riboflavin (10 mg), pyridoxine HCl (3 mg), vitamin B₁₂ (15 mcg), niacinamide (100 mg), calcium pantothenate (50 mg), folic acid (1.5 mg), biotin (100 mcg), ascorbic acid (150 mg).

The standard solutions of vitamin were prepared from the following salts. B₁ : thiamine hydrochloride (batch no. 9048) of Central Drug House, Mumbai; B₂ : riboflavin (batch no. 970) and B₆ : pyridoxine hydrochloride (batch no. 1252), both from Ases Chemical Works, Jodhpur.

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